

ANALYSIS OF VARIATION PATTERNS IN LINEAR DENSITY OF FALSE-TWISTED YARN DURING TENSILE ELONGATION UNTIL BREAKAGE

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Abstract. *The article theoretically studies the factors affecting the quality indicators of the pneumatically spun yarn during the process of false twisting, the values of the linear density of the yarn. The effect of increasing the degree of yarn breakage and reducing the weight of the fibers involved in the spinning process on the relative stiffness of the yarn is studied. Also, the deformation moduli of the yarn when the maximum value is reached are analyzed using a graph-analytical method.*

Key words: *Yarn, false twist, yarn quality parameters, yarn linear density, deformation modulus, deformation value.*

Аннотация. *В статье теоретически исследованы факторы, влияющие на показатели качества пневмопряденой пряжи при ложной крутке, значения линейной плотности пряжи. Исследовано влияние повышения обрывности пряжи и снижения массы волокон, участвующих в прядении, на относительную жёсткость пряжи. Также графоаналитическим методом проанализированы модули деформации пряжи при достижении максимального значения.*

Ключевые слова: *пряжа, ложная крутка, показатели качества пряжи, линейная плотность пряжи, модуль деформации, величина деформации.*

Introduction. During the twisting process of a pneumatically spun yarn, the fibers are subjected to effects such as stretching and bending. Each of these deformations consists of three parts: elastic, elastic and plastic. Due to the return of elastic and elastic deformations, an elastic rotation occurs in the yarn, directed in the opposite direction to its twisting, which tends to

unwind and form tangles. This situation complicates the further processing of the yarn in production, especially in the production of textile products [1,2].

Analysis of the properties of the yarn spun by the pneumatic-mechanical method shows that it is superior to the yarn made by the ring method in some indicators. Despite the high twist, it has a lower density and a more porous structure, which to some extent limits its scope of application [3]. In particular, due to the low density of the yarn, pneumatic-mechanical machines are not used in the re-combing spinning system. In the production of yarn with a low linear density by the indicated method, for the technical and economic efficiency of the spinning machines, it is necessary to sharply increase the frequency of rotation of the chambers, which leads to a higher than normal consumption of electric energy [4]. There are two factors that reduce the linear density of the yarn: an increase in the degree of yarn breakage and a decrease in the relative density of the yarn with a decrease in the weight of the fibers involved in the spinning process.

The elongation at break of yarn produced on a pneumatic spinning machine is 1.5-2% higher than that of yarn produced on ring machines. The greatest difference in elongation is observed in yarn made of cotton, while it is less common in viscose and synthetic fibers. The linear density unevenness is in the range of 10 to 14%, and these indicators are superior to those of yarn obtained from the re-carding system. Yarn spun by the pneumatic method has a volume of 10-15% more than yarn obtained by the ring method, better heat retention, is more resistant to abrasion, and has fewer defects. The limited use of yarn spun by the pneumatic method is primarily associated with its low strength and density, high twist, therefore, we consider it appropriate to study the reasons that cause these characteristics.

Research Methods. The modulus of a yarn with a false twist is a function of the deformation parameters $\varepsilon_N, \varepsilon_e, \varepsilon_m, \varepsilon_S$ and ε_k , which are the change function $E(\varepsilon)$. In order to determine the values of the deformation modulus of a yarn with different values of the linear density of the yarn, T , by calculating the values of the elongation to break of the yarn, it is necessary to determine the dependence of these parameters on the linear density. For this, we again use the results of the experiments presented below:

Table 1.

Average values of deformation parameter ε_e and linear density for groups T

Number of groups	1	2	3	4	5	6
T_{sr}, Tex	28,10	28,60	29,03	29,27	29,56	31,30
ε_e	0,00044	0,00020	0,00170	0,00060	0,00082	0,00180

Fig 1. Variation of deformations ε_e of a pneumatically spun yarn depending on the linear density

As shown in Figure 1, the initial value of the deformation E_N is determined from the values of the $E(\epsilon)$ graph obtained from the experiments at $\epsilon_N = 0,00025$, i.e. at a value very close to zero. Therefore, the value of ϵ_N is assumed to be zero in all cases, i.e. $\epsilon_N = 0$. E_N is the deformation modulus of the undeformed yarn at $\epsilon_N = 0$. However, the value of E_N at $\epsilon_N = 0$ cannot be determined. Therefore, when determining the E_N modulus, a value close to zero is taken for the deformation. Let us consider the dependence of $E(\epsilon)$ on the linear density of the yarn on the change in other deformation parameters.

Research Results. Figure 1 shows the dependence of the linear density of a yarn with a false twist on the value of the deformation modulus E_e . Here, the curve is constructed according to the given actual values of ϵ_e and T , that is, it shows the actual change in the parameter ϵ_e from the actual values of the linear density of the yarn used in the experiment.

As can be seen from Figure 1, the change in the curve is completely random and does not correspond to any analytical description. By averaging the values of ϵ_e and T for the groups of linear densities of the yarn, we obtain from the data given in Table 1.

Curve 2 in Figure 1 is obtained using the values of ϵ_e and T_{sr} given in Table 1. According to the nature of curve 2, it can be said that the value of ϵ_e can increase with increasing linear density of the yarn. Analytically, curve 2 can be described by a more complex function. However, for simplicity, we will approximate it with a linear function in the figure below:

$$\epsilon_e(T) = a_e + b_e T \tag{1}$$

where $a_e = 0,000321$; $b_e = 0,000034 \text{ tex}^{-1}$ – coefficients determined by the least squares method based on the dependence (1). Line 3 in Figure 1 is constructed using formula (1) by setting the value of T from zero to 160 tex in 10 tex steps. As can be seen from Figure 1, line 3 is actually an average straight line for curve 2. Thus, the parameters of the function $E(\epsilon)$ are actually averaged three times. First, we average the dependence $F(\epsilon)$, we obtain the average dependence $F(\epsilon)$. Next, curve 1 in Figure 1 is averaged and curve 2 is obtained (Figure 1). Then, averaging curve 2, we obtain line 3, which is described by equation (1).

Such a three-fold averaging of the functions $E(\epsilon)$, i.e. $E_N, E_e, E_m, E_S, E_k, \epsilon_e, \epsilon_m, \epsilon_S$ and ϵ_k , with respect to all other parameters, simplifies the variation of these parameters depending on the linear density of the yarn, and this shows that this averaging is appropriate and correct. Moreover, it can be noted that they are, in fact, regularities of the variation of these parameters depending on the linear density of the yarn. Moreover, this averaging is a three-fold statistical processing of the data obtained from the results of the experiments presented in the Appendix.

Figure 2 shows the changes in the deformation parameter ϵ_m , at which the deformation modulus of the yarn E reaches a maximum value E_m from the values of the linear density of the yarn T .

Here too, curve 1 is the actual variation of ϵ_m as a function of T .

Fig. 2. Variation of the deformation ε_m value depending on the linear density of the yarn
 Curve 2 – Variation of the average values of ε_m and T for the groups of linear densities given in Table 2.

Table 2

Average values of the deformation parameter ε_m and linear density of the yarn by groups T

Number of groups	1	2	3	4	5	6
T_{sr}, Tex	28,10	28,60	29,03	29,27	29,56	31,30
ε_m	0,01097	0,00845	0,00960	0,00579	0,01927	0,01496

Line 3 in Figure 2 is an approximation of curve 2, just as in the previous case,

$$\varepsilon_m(T) = a_m + b_m T \tag{2}$$

where $a_m = 0,006054$; $b_m = 0,000125 \text{ tex}^{-1}$ - coefficients whose values are determined by the least squares method,

Fig. 3. Change in the value of deformation ε_s depending on the linear density of the thread

Figure 3 shows the correlations obtained based on the processing of experimental results (Appendix, Figure 1-45-s).

Curve 1 is obtained from the actual values of ε_s for the actual linear densities. Curve 2 is obtained from the average values of T and ε_s for the linear density groups shown in Table 3.

Table 3

Average values of deformation parameter ε_s and linear density of yarn by groups T

Number of groups	1	2	3	4	5	6
T_{sr}, Tex	28,10	28,60	29,03	29,27	29,56	31,30
ε_s	0,0320	0,0412	0,0205	0,0303	0,0154	0,0407

Curve 3 in Figure 3 is an approximate representation of curve 2, as in the previous case,

$$\varepsilon_s(T) = a_s + b_s T \tag{3}$$

where $a_s = 0,022211$; $b_s = 0,000235 \text{ tex}^{-1}$ are the coefficients determined using the least squares method.

Discussion. As can be seen from the figures (Appendix, Figure 1-45-s), in some cases, after reaching the maximum value, the deformation modulus of the yarn decreases monotonically, while in other cases, after reaching a certain value $\varepsilon = \varepsilon_s$, the modulus of the yarn remains approximately constant or increases. To determine this value ε , the value of ε_s is introduced.

1. After the deformation modulus of the yarn reaches $E = E_m$, its value decreases intensively, and starting from the deformation value $\varepsilon = \varepsilon_s$, the deformation intensity decreases.

2. After the deformation modulus of the yarn reaches $E = E_m$, its value decreases, and after $\varepsilon = \varepsilon_s$, the value of E remains almost constant.

3. After the deformation modulus of the yarn reaches $E = E_m$, its value decreases, and after $\varepsilon = \varepsilon_s$, the value of the yarn modulus increases to a certain value.

However, after taking the average values of E_s and E_k for the groups of linear densities of cotton yarns, we obtain the data presented in Table 4.

As can be seen from Table 4, the average values of the linear density of the yarn T_{sr} in these two cases differ. This is because in some experiments on yarn elongation, there were cases of failure in the experiments. In general, the values of T_{sr} are quite close. The value of E_s is greater than E_k in all cases, except for the first group of linear densities. This means that in these cases, after reaching the deformation modulus, the value of E increases, then in this case after $E = E_s$ the yarn stiffens, that is, the value of the deformation modulus E increases. In this case, cotton yarns with small linear densities $T_{sr} = 17.0 \text{ tex}$ ($4.0 \leq T \leq 18.5 \text{ tex}$) are included.

Table 4

Comparatively evaluated values of deformation moduli E_s and E_k of pneumatically spun yarn with linear yarn density groups

Number of groups	1	2	3	4	5	6
T_{sr} , Tex	28,10	28,60	29,03	29,27	29,56	31,30
E_s , MPa	2855,87	2543,70	1911,81	2844,20	2039,91	3249,20
T_{sr} , Tex	28,10	28,60	29,03	29,27	29,56	31,30
E_k , MPa	2733,09	2449,30	2102,99	3087,11	2075,43	3062,30

Figure 4 shows the variation of the $E_s(T)$ curve 1 and $E_k(T)$ curve 2 functions constructed based on the data presented in Table 4.

Fig. 4. Variation of the deformation modulus E_s and E_k depending on the linear density of the yarn

As can be seen from Figure 4, in the range of linear densities $T \leq 22 \text{ tex}$ $E_k > E_s$. In such cases, another extreme point (ε_s, E_s) appears in the $E(\varepsilon)$ dependence. When describing the change in $E(\varepsilon)$ by equation, this extreme point should be taken into account, especially since the $E(\varepsilon)$ curve is estimated only using the extreme points of the $E(\varepsilon)$ curves. In general, taking into account the point (ε_s, E_s) in any case helps to better estimate the $E(\varepsilon)$ curves at any values of the linear density of the yarn.

The change in the critical value of the deformation ε_k at the time of yarn breakage depending on the linear density of the yarn is shown in Figure 5.

Fig. 5. Variation of the deformation ϵ_k of the yarn depending on the linear density

Here, curve 1 also describes the change in the critical strain ϵ_k depending on the actual linear density of the thread. This curve is constructed according to the data in Table 2.2. As can be seen from Figure 5, this curve also varies in a complex, stochastic manner and does not correspond to any analytical description. Curve 2 in Figure 5 is constructed according to the average data of the values of T and ϵ_k for the linear density groups given in Table 5.

Table 5

Average values of the deformation parameter ϵ_k and linear density of the yarn by groups T

Number of groups	1	2	3	4	5	6
T_{sr}, Tex	28,10	28,60	29,03	29,27	29,56	31,30
ϵ_k	0,04834	0,04907	0.07012	0,07594	0,07145	0,06133

A certain regularity is observed in the nature of the change in curve 2 (Fig. 5). This curve is also approximated in the form of a linear function

$$\epsilon_k(T) = a_k + b_k T \tag{4}$$

where the values of a_k and b_k are determined by the method of least squares and are equal to: $a_k = 0,056204$; $b_k = 0,000453 \text{ tex}^{-1}$.

As can be seen from Figure 5, line 3, constructed according to formula (4), describes curve 2 with satisfactory accuracy.

The value of the critical strain ϵ_k for each thread with a certain linear density is a constant value. The values of ϵ_k for different linear density values are determined using formula (4).

Conclusion. Thus, for specific values of the linear density of the yarn T, the specific values of the function parameters $E(\epsilon)$ - E_N , E_e , E_m , E_S , E_k , ϵ_e , ϵ_m , ϵ_S , and ϵ_k ($\epsilon_N = 0$) are determined from equations (4). Using equations with specific values of these parameters, the change in the deformation modulus for yarns with a given linear density T is approximately estimated depending on the values of the longitudinal deformation ϵ when the yarn is stretched to break. Equations (4), we recall once again, are valid only for yarns produced on a rotor spinning machine from medium-fiber cotton of grade 1, 1st wicking group, 4th fiber type in a carded spinning system. For yarns obtained by other technological methods and from other varieties of cotton, the parameters of the function $E(\epsilon)$ and the values of equations (4) should be re-established based on the results of experiments on stretching these yarns to breaking point and the results of their processing according to the above method.

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